

“TECHNICAL REPORT”

OVERHAULING OF PACKER

PRESENTED TO

THE NIGERIAN SOCIETY OF ENGINEERS (NSE)

BY

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IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE REGISTRATION AS A
CORPERATE MEMBER OF THE NIGERIAN SOCIETY OF ENGINEERS

APRIL, 2020.

CERTIFICATE OF SUBMISSION

This is to certify that I OGUNDEJI OLANREWAJU MICHAEL has written this report myself and it is true account of my training and working experience.

Signature of candidate and date

Name of Candidate

Signature of Senior Engineer and date

Name of Senior Engineer

DEDICATION

I dedicate this report to The Almighty God for His love, guidance and protection.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

My appreciation goes to the Head of my Unit Engr. Smart Odaro who is the Packaging Engineer of International breweries Plc, Ilesa and others whose without their efforts this project won't be a successful one,

The first on the list is Engr. Ugah Chukwuma, Mr Philips (Baba Experience), Ossai Walter from international Breweries Plc, Ilesa.

I also wish to acknowledge my senior colleagues in the Nigerian Society of Engineers Ilesha chapter for their guidance and wise council on how to join the Society and how to properly write the report. They are; Engr. (Mrs) Mojirade Oluruntoba, Engr. Taiwo, Engr. Kareem Muyideen and Engr Yomi.

And to my special woman Obembe Olamide Inumidun , I can't thank you enough for your kindness and support, you inspire me a lot.

SUMMARY

This report is the summary of a project I participated in July 2015. This report covers every aspect of the project. It is majorly a maintenance project which means our interest was only about restoring the performance of the machine to its original state. There was no attempt to change or alter its original features.

The different stages of this project was adequately discussed in this report, most importantly, safety around the work place from PPEs to safety behavior was also discussed. The Bill of Engineering Measurement and Evaluation of the project was prepared to give a sense of what the cost of the project looks like. Pictures and diagrams of parts used and the machine respectively were also provided in the report.

This report is a true reflection of part of the experiences I have gained in International Breweries PLC. My professional experiences have been in the area of operations and maintenance. Therefore, I have decided to document my experience in the overhaul of Packer or Crater in this report.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PACKAGING MACHINES

In the course of my work over the years, I have performed maintenance on all the machines at one time or the other. Apart from performing maintenance on the machines, I also have operational knowledge of all the machines. From experience, having operational knowledge of a machine will enhance an Engineer's or Technician's skill in the area of repair.

The machines are as follows;

1.1.1 Depalletizer: Used bottles from the market as well as new bottles from manufacturers are supplied to the company in vehicle, loaded on wooden materials called pallet. The pallet containing specified number of crates with bottles is brought in by forklift. The machine called Depalletizer unloads the crates of empties from pallets and puts them on the conveyor which carries the crates away.

1.1.2 Unpacker/Decrater/Decaser: Empty bottles in crates are brought on a conveyor from a Depalletizer to the front of the Unpacker. The Unpacker removes the bottles from the crates into an arrangement of conveyors which carries the bottles to the next machine. The empty crates from which bottles are removed continue their journey on the conveyor through the crate washer where they are washed, to the packer where they are refilled with full bottles. Detailed discussion on the Unpacker will be done in the later chapters.

1.1.3 Bottle Washer: The unpacker transfers the bottles to the washer where they are washed and cleaned of dirt and contaminants rendering them sterile or near sterile. Bottle washing removes all dirt (physical contamination) and bacteria (microbiological contamination) from the bottles. Bottle washing is important in ensuring that the container is clean and free of bacteria. The factors that affect cleaning are mechanical action, temperature, and detergent and soak time.

1.1.4 Empty Bottle Inspector: Washed empty bottles are inspected with a view to removing foreign bottles, chipped mouth, bottle containing dirt at the side or the bottom, bottle with damaged lock ring and bottle containing residual liquid.

1.1.5 Filler/Crowner: This is a two-in-one machine where washed and inspected bottles from the washer and EBI are filled with beer or malt thereafter crowned. The filler is the production rated machine in the entire packaging hall or probably the brewery output as a whole. In order words, the efficiency of the packaging process depends on the efficiency of the filler/crowner. One of the jobs I have done on the filler is the replacement of a bearing on the intermediate star wheel central column

Fig 1.1 Star wheel central column space.

The space in the figure above is the position of the star wheel central column. It is held in position with four bolts.

Fig 1.2 Star wheel central column.

The figure above represents the star wheel central column; it has two bearings, one at the top and the other below. The bearings were to be replaced because one of it collapsed. It is driven by a wheel (gear) located under the table. This central column is carrying the star wheel. While it rotates, the star wheel will be moving bottles to the filling valves.

Fig 1.3 Star wheel central column (replaced)

The figure above shows where the central column has been replaced after the collapsed bearing was changed. The central column is now inside the housing.

1.1.6 Preliminary Filled Bottle Inspector (PFBI): Filled bottles inspector which checks for fill and lack of crown cork.

1.1.7 Pasteurizer: This is the machine designed to kill all pathogenic microorganisms still in the beverage after filling them by increasing the shelf life of the product.

1.1.8 Labeller: The machine sticks labels on the bottles. Bottles are labelled for identification, attractiveness as well as advertisement.

1.1.9 Labelled Bottles Inspector: Checks for unlabelled and uncorked and low filled bottles.

1.1.10 Packer/Crate/Caser: This machine is the exact opposite of the unpacker in function. The packer receives the filled and labelled bottles from the labeller, arranges them into crates arriving from the crate washer.

1.1.11 Palletizer: The crates containing the filled, corked and labelled bottles are arranged on a pallet.

1.2 SPEED RELATIONSHIP OF THE PACKAGING MACHINES

The filler is the reference machine that determines the speed or capacity of other machines in the hall. All machines before the filler (Depalletizer, Unpacker, Washer, EBI) must have higher speed than the filler in descending order, while machines after it must also have higher speed in ascending order thereby

forming the letter V where the filler is at the bottom of the V. this system ensures that the filler makes a fairly continuous run and does not have to wait to be supplied with bottles, ie the filler must be fed with bottles at sufficient rate and would not also have to wait for bottles to be evacuated from it. Constant stoppage of the filler affects the filling process and the filler is a reference machine.

Fig 1.4 Speed Relationship of the Packaging machine.

1.3 BASIC PACKAGING PRINCIPLES

Before going into the project proper; Overhauling of Packer I will like to paint a picture of my work environment. This discussion will be limited to the packaging section of the supply function. They are

other departments that complement the effort of the packaging department to bring about the products consumers enjoy but for the purpose of this report; their functions will not be discussed.

The packaging hall is a section of the brewery where products are packaged in containers. Inside the packaging hall are the packaging lines. A packaging line is an arrangement of specialized machines whose specific functions are linked and the machines themselves are also linked by a network of conveyors. A single arrangement of a set of these machines makes one packaging line while two or more make two or more lines. A line starts at empty bottles supply into the hall and ends at filled bottles removal from the hall.

1.4 THE PACKER

The Packer is a robot whose work is to remove the bottles from the Crates and puts it on a Conveyor which will transport it to the bottle washer. This particular machine that was overhauled is a product of Kronos, a German Company. It is a fully automated machine. The machine can be divided into 3 major parts

- i. The robot
- ii. The table
- iii. The indexing Conveyor

The Robot is mainly a frame which is attached to a gripper head (the part that picks bottles). The main frame makes a front and back movement while the gripper head make an up, down and cross-slide movement.

The table is a system of Conveyor chains driven by an electric motor. It is the place where the bottles picked from the crates are dropped. The indexing Conveyor is the Conveyor system that arranges the Crates for the gripper head to pick the bottles.

Fig 1.5The Packer Machine

1.5 Reasons for Overhauling the Packer

The Packer does not rest as far as production is taking place. Moreover, International Breweries PLC as a FMCG operates round the clock and due to this fact, the rate of maintenance of the machine has to be high. As a machine that runs round the clock, the rate of wear and tear increases which automatically lowers the performance of the machine. When the performance of the machine decreases, the operator tends to work more with no additional result.

Having said this, the reasons for overhauling the Packer include:

- i. To restore the machine to its original status
- ii. To increase its performance
- iii. To increase its reliability
- iv. To reduce downtime caused by the machine
- v. To increase productivity
- vi. To reduce the stress witnessed by the operator.

1.6 **Scope of the Project**

The scope of the overhaul is the extent that the overhaul covered. The overhaul was all about servicing some parts of the machine and replacement of worn parts. During the overhaul, the Packer was not completely overhauled, but some specific parts of the machine was identified and worked on. None of the parts used was fabricated by us or locally manufactured rather, they were parts from the OEM (original equipment manufacturer).

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 WORK PLACE SAFETY

2.1 Safety at Work.

Before discussing the actual technical work that was done during the overhaul, I will like to first and foremost discuss issues around safety and safety behaviors during the overhaul.

In Engineering, it is said that safety is first, so whenever we are on duty or about to do anything, we think safety first. Hence, during the overhaul which lasted for about 2 weeks we observed the safety culture in the area of using Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), Safe Access to Machines (SAM) and lock out and Tag out (LOTO).

2.2 List of Personal Protective Equipment used:

- 1) Safety boot: for the protection of the foot
- 2) Hand Gloves: for the protection of the hand.
- 3) Eye Google: for the protection of the eyes.
- 4) Overall: for covering of the entire body against injury
- 5) Ear plug: To protect the eardrum against excessive noise.

Fig 2.1. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Other Safety Practices Observed during the Overhaul are:

- i. Lock Out and Tag Out: this is the practice of shutting down a machine and locking the switch with a special lock out pad lock and thereafter put a tag with an inscription “Do Not Operate” to alert everyone to stir clear from operating the machine except the person that locked it.
- ii. Work at height: work at height is any work above 2m. We ensured that any work at height was done with an appropriate procedure and equipment.
- iii. Lifting or carrying of heavy objects was done with the help of a Jack, trolley or forklift.

Fig 2.2. Access to Machine and Lock-Tag-Try Procedure.

The actual work that was done during the overhaul can be categorized into four stages.

- i. Shut down
- ii. Dismounting of parts equipment
- iii. Assembling with new parts
- iv. Test running and fine tuning.

2.3 Shutdown

This is the first stage in the overhauling project; it involves putting off the machine and the adjourning Conveyors according to the Shutdown SOP (Standard Operating Procedure). Additionally, the isolators were switched off in compliance to SAM (Safe access to Machines). It was at this stage that LOTO (Lock Out and Tag Out) was performed.

2.4 Dismounting of Equipment

When the safety of team members was guaranteed, dismounting of the equipment commenced. The parts of the equipment where this was done are the Packer table and the indexing Conveyor since the grab head was already removed before shutdown. Parts that were removed from the Packer table are:

- i. The transfer plate was removed by loosening the fasteners
- ii. The Conveyor chains were removed by cutting them with Conveyor punch and a ball pin hammer
- iii. The wear strips
- iv. The sprockets were removed using Allen key 6
- v. The electric motor (Drive), bearings and drive shaft were removed.
- vi. Underlining rollers and lubrication pipe under the table were removed.
- vii. The idler shaft, rollers and half bearing were removed.

Parts removed from the indexing Conveyor are

- i. Indexing Conveyor chains
- ii. Wear strips
- iii. Idler shaft and rollers
- iv. Drive shaft and sprockets
- v. Bearings
- vi. Electric motor and drive chain
- vii. Transfer wedges
- viii. Crate guides

Parts that were removed from the main frame (Robot), mostly bearings, were removed and replaced immediately.

After the dismounting was completed, thorough washing of all the parts removed was done so that good ones can be selected and re-used. The machine was also thoroughly inspected so as to identify defects like wear, corroded parts, bent parts etc.

2.5 Assembling with New Parts.

The third stage in the overhaul was the assembling with new parts. The main frame was the first section of the machine to be assembled. The assembling that was done on the mainframe was replacement of the bearings. The bearings were changed by balancing the mainframe with a wood and a “monkey jack” so that the frame stayed in position while the bearing was changed. This particular task was done with a great deal of caution and expertise.

The table was the next section to be assembled after the main frame. The table is the section of the machine with the most number of unassembled parts. Therefore, more time was spent in assembling it with the new parts.

The first part that was assembled was the idler shaft. This was assembled with a 40X25T roller before it was installed in its position in front of the machine with a 19mm diameter bolt at both ends. The drive shaft was also installed at the opposite end of the table the same way the idler was installed. Thereafter, 17 pieces of 40X25T sprockets was coupled on it. The electric motor (Drive) was installed at the left end of the shaft.

The underlining rollers which ensures that the table Conveyor chains are tensioned and firm on the sprocket and idler rollers were the next parts to be fixed. It was fixed under the Packer table. Thereafter, the Conveyor chains were connected. After the chains were connected, the transfer plate was fixed at the discharge end of the table. The work of the transfer plate is to enable smooth transfer of bottles from the table to the transverse conveyor attached to the table. The transfer plate was the last part to be fixed on the table. The last section of the machine to be assembled was the indexing Conveyor. At the indexing Conveyor, the 30mm idler shaft and drive shaft which are at the in feed and discharge ends respectively of the indexing Conveyor were change because the old ones were worn. The shafts were coupled with corresponding rollers and sprockets. The conveyor rail was fixed with profile and wear strips before it was installed in its position. The conveyor chain was thereafter connected. The crate guide which was removed during dismembering stage was returned to its position without any amendment on it. The indexing conveyor drive chain was changed as well. These changes marked the end of the assembling stage.

Fig 2.3 40x25T Roller.

Fig 2.4 40x25T Roller (plan view).

Fig 2.3 and fig 2.4 are the pictures of the roller that were used during the overhaul of the Packer. They were used on the Packer table as well as the indexing conveyor.

Fig 2.5 40x25T Sprocket (plan view)

Fig 2.6 40x25T sprocket

Fig 2.5 and 2.6 are the sprockets that were used on the Packer table. Seventeen of it was used. It was coupled on the drive shaft. Its work is to drive the network of chains on the Packer table. It was also used on the indexing conveyor.

2.6 Test Running and fine tuning:

This is the last stage of the overhaul activities. It is done to know the effectiveness of the overhaul. In this stage, the first thing that was done was to unlock the machine which was locked in the beginning for safety reasons. The isolators were turned on and the machine was powered up. The table and lubrication pipes which were removed during dismembering stage were returned to ensure adequate lubrication. The grab head which was also removed to ensure enough space and safety of workers was returned to its position. When the machine finished booting, it was run on manual mode for some time to ensure that all the moving parts are free and running well. Thereafter, some crates were sent into the machine so as the run it on Auto mode. On Auto mode, it was discovered that the grab head was crashing on the Crates which was as a result of misalignment. This misalignment we discovered was caused by the Crate guide. On the discovery, the guide was well adjusted and the crashing stopped. The successful test-running of the machine marked the end of the overhaul. At the end of the project, the Packer was handed over to the packaging department for commencement of production.

2.7 Problems Encountered

During the overhaul project, problems were encountered just like any other human endeavor. Though the challenges were few due to the through and careful planning of the project.

The problems encountered were as follows;

- I. Most of the ordered spare parts could not arrive on time.
- II. Some bolts could not fit in.
- III. The time planned for the project was cut short making us to work under pressure.

2.8 Solution Proffered

The few problems encountered were not left unresolved. The solutions proffered are;

- a. To solve the problem of unavailable spare parts, some not-too-bad old ones were selected and re-used.
- b. Some oversized bolts were fabricated to size.
- c. When time was running out, we decided to extend our working hours so as to meet up with expectations.

2.9 Knowledge Gained

Participating in the overhaul project increased and improved my professional experience. The knowledge gained is in the areas of Measurement, fabrication, planning, Bearing replacement and shaft balancing.

Fig 2.7 Gantt chart of the overhauling of Packer

The Gantt chart provides the schedule of the project at a glance. It helped us to easily monitor the progress of the job. All activities carried out are represented on the chart.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 BILL OF ENGINEERING MEASUREMENT AND EVALUATION FOR THE PROJECT.

Table 3.1 BILL OF ENGINEERING MEASUREMENT AND EVALUATION

S/NO	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIALS	QTY	UNIT	RATE (₦)	AMOUNT(₦)
1	CONVEYOR CHAIN	51	m	26000	1326000
2	40X23T SPROCKET	17	pcs	28000	476000
3	40X23T ROLLER	17	pcs	7500	127500
4	30X25T SPROCKET	2	pcs	28000	56000
5	30X25T ROLLER	2	pcs	7500	15000
6	40mm BEARING	2	pcs	23000	46000
7	30mm BEARING	2	pcs	23000	46000
8	PILLOW BEARING(40mm)	2	pcs	62000	124000
9	TRANSFER PLATE	1	pcs	350000	350000
10	DRIVE CHAIN(3/4 link)	3	m	110000	330000
11	WEAR STRIP 1	30	m	2500	75000
12	WEAR STRIP 2	16	m	1200	19200
13	COUNTER SUNK BOLT	8	M6	55	440
14	UNSKILLED LABOR	12		900	10800
15	SKILLED LABOR	20		4000	80000
	SUB TOTAL				3081940
	CONTINGENCIES (5%)				154097
	TOTAL				3236037
	VAT (5%)				161801.85
	GRAND TOTAL				3397838.85

From the table above it can be seen that the project cost is three million three hundred and ninety seven thousand eight hundred and thirty eight naira and eighty five kobo. A contingency of 5% was provided in the calculation. The project would have cost more but for the fact that we re-used some of the parts that were still in good condition. We did that to save cost for the company.

CHAPTER FOUR

8.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

8.1 CONCLUSION

The overhaul of packer was successful because the objective of the project was realized. When operation of the machines resumed, it worked at installed capacity which is an indication and a testimony that the projects were successful. During the period of the overhaul, the issue of safety of workers was taken seriously which accounts for the fact that no accident was recorded. The management of materials was also considered bearing in mind that material wastage is a cost to the company.

8.2 RECOMMENDATION

Overhaul is a shutdown maintenance which is a very costly project. For full benefits of this type of maintenance I wish to recommend as follows;

- i. That companies that can afford it should go for it because it is an effective avenue of transferring knowledge and skills from more experienced Engineers to the less experienced ones.
- ii. That enough product that will last throughout the period of the project be stocked in the warehouse for the sales team before shutting down.
- iii. Any company that adopts this type of maintenance should carry it out at a time in the year when their sales is lowest.
- iv. Adequate planning and budgeting be done towards the project.
- v. In the view of reducing cost, companies should depend less on OEMs and this can be achieved by improving Reverse Engineering practice.

APPENDIX a. Packer

Appendix b. Filler

Appendix c. Labeller

Appendix d. Pasteurizer

Appendix e. Palletizer.

APPENDIX f. Bottle Washer

